

Carbon payback time for residential building replacements in Zurich under the stock-level consequential replacement LCA

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Abstract. This study proposes a stock-level method combining Consequential Replacement LCA (CRLCA) and range-bound analysis to assess the carbon payback time (CPBT) of large-scale construction strategies. Extending CRLCA beyond individual cases enhances representativeness and policy relevance. Leveraging stable stock-level population dynamics, the study introduces a per capita metric alongside the conventional per area approach, highlighting the individual dimension of carbon impact. Against the backdrop of Switzerland's *inward development* policy, the study examines 335 residential building replacement (BR) projects in Zurich (2001–2019), compared with two assumed refurbishment-based alternatives. Results show a CPBT of approximately 16 years per area and 21 years per capita for BR under the most optimistic carbon assumptions. Even in this best-case scenario, BR fails to achieve payback for post-2019 decisions, as decarbonization reduces new buildings' operational advantage. This pattern holds for public buildings, where BR performs even worse. Per capita metrics yield more conservative outcomes than per area metrics under identical conditions, underscoring the importance of metric choice and its role in linking individual accountability to more inclusive, citizen-informed policymaking. Thus, this study supports prioritizing refurbishment over replacement as a climate-conscious urban renewal strategy and stresses that construction strategies are time-sensitive to decarbonization and must be reassessed as conditions evolve.

1. Introduction

Building Replacement (BR), involving demolition and immediate reconstruction of structures on the same site, is a key urban renewal strategy that facilitates spatial transformation, increases urban density, and improves building performance. This approach is often promoted as a means to replace aging, energy-inefficient buildings with more efficient alternatives. However, growing emphasis on whole-life carbon thinking has challenged this rationale. While BR may reduce operational emissions, it entails substantial embodied emissions, raising the question of whether replacement is truly more environmentally sustainable than refurbishment [1]. This debate reflects a broader bias in earlier Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs), which conventionally prioritized operational over embodied impacts. A second bias is the dominant focus on new construction, with little attention paid to existing buildings and interventions in them [2, 3]. As a result, older buildings are frequently written off prematurely for their perceived energy inefficiency, especially given the dominance of energy efficiency metrics in sustainability discourse [4].

Research on the LCA of existing buildings, including repair, refurbishment, rebuilding, or replacement, remains limited in both quantity and methodological consistency [3]. In addition

to inconsistencies in terminology and referenced data, two core challenges persist: (1) variation in the choice of LCA approach, with most studies relying on attributional LCA (ALCA), while consequential LCA (CLCA) has recently gained traction in the field; and (2) inconsistency in system boundary definitions, with substantial variation in what is included within the assessment scope. These methodological disparities hinder cross-study comparability and complicate efforts to determine which strategy is most environmentally preferable in a given context.

Huuhka *et al.* [3] therefore proposed the **Consequential Replacement LCA** (CRLCA), a CLCA subtype that evaluates the impacts of replacing an existing building or continuing its use, aiming to harmonize assessment practices and inform strategic decision-making. CRLCA focuses on forward-looking, decision-driven outcomes by excluding historical emissions. It offers two key advantages: (1) **decision-focused causality**, as it captures only the direct environmental consequences of a given choice while disregarding emissions unaffected by the choice, thereby enabling clearer causal attribution than ALCA; and (2) **time-sensitive comparability**, as it allows the comparison of strategies within a consistent time frame that reflects actual decision points and durations, thereby addressing the temporal misalignment in ALCA’s cumulative lifetime perspective. This feature makes CRLCA well-suited for assessing emission balancing dynamics, which is highly sensitive to decision timing amid ongoing decarbonization.

Nevertheless, CRLCA studies, like earlier LCAs on replacement or refurbishment, remain at the single-building scale—useful for owners deciding on one asset, but offering limited policy insight due to low representativeness. By contrast, stock-level analysis supports decision-makers overseeing building portfolios—such as urban planners and national authorities responsible for climate goals—by offering comparative insights on strategy timing and effectiveness, thereby informing more integrated, long-term planning. This study therefore applies CRLCA at the stock level to compare the carbon effects of portfolio-scale refurbishment versus replacement. Although not originally designed to capture all consequences of large-scale decisions [3], its stock-level application here focuses exclusively on building-related environmental impacts; broader effects, including land use, infrastructure, and mobility, lie beyond the defined system boundaries.

This study examines residential building replacement (RBR) under Switzerland’s Spatial Planning Act and its *inward development* (*Innenentwicklung*) policy [5]. Introduced in 2013 and reinforced in 2023, the policy mandates densification under re-urbanization to protect greenfield land and biodiversity by blocking peripheral expansion, making replacement the leading strategy in Swiss major cities [6]. RBR represents over one-third of Zurich’s replacement volume (2001–2019) [6], and residential buildings are a key focus of national energy optimization. A total of 335 RBR projects are selected, each comprising exclusively residential buildings, with 628 demolished and 556 newly constructed. Two refurbishment-based alternatives are modelled alongside BR to comparatively assess carbon impacts and identify the environmentally preferable option, with **Carbon Payback Time** (CPBT) as the evaluation indicator. This analysis adopts the comparative CPBT formulation by Huuhka [3], which expresses the relative advantage between strategies as $CPBT = \Delta G_e / \Delta G_o$, where ΔG_e and ΔG_o denote differences in embodied and operational emissions, respectively. CPBT is calculated separately using cumulative emissions per capita and per floor area, enabling robust analysis and offering distinct perspectives on environmental performance at both user and building levels. This study contributes to the ongoing debate over replacement versus refurbishment, guided by the following questions: (i) Is BR less carbon-intensive than refurbishment? (ii) How do different metrics influence the assessment outcomes? (iii) How can CRLCA be scaled from individual to stock level?

2. Methods

Among the 335 RBR projects, demolished buildings were constructed between 1844 and the early 1980s, and new buildings completed between 2001 and 2019, with a gross floor area (GFA)-weighted average completion year of 2013.2. The dataset, provided by the Zurich Statistics Office, includes construction year, floor area, volume, height, and population data recorded

three years before demolition and after redevelopment. However, construction material-related information such as specifications and quantity is not available. In this study, the completion year of new buildings is treated as the decision time in the CRLCA framework.

2.1. Stock-level scenario definitions

Three scenarios, namely **BR**(Building Replacement), **RN**(Refurbishment with New Construction), and **RO**(Refurbishment of Original Buildings), are formulated to represent distinct construction strategies for carbon impact comparison, as illustrated in Figure 1. RN and BR operate within Zurich’s re-urbanization context, characterized by population and built space growth. While BR pursues densification within the existing built-up area in line with the *inward development* policy [6], RN offers an alternative by utilizing vacant land beyond the built-up area to accommodate the same population ($P_1 + P_2$). In RN, additional residential space for incoming residents (P_2) is built to BR’s new construction standards, ensuring consistency in per capita space allocation. In contrast, RO entails no re-urbanization, with a stable population size P_1 and no additional spatial demand. Scenarios without refurbishment are excluded, as most aging residential buildings in Switzerland must undergo energy upgrades under the CO2 Act.

Stock-level analysis capitalizes on stable population dynamics to adopt *per capita* as a functional unit—an approach newly introduced in this line of research. Although user fluctuation may introduce uncertainty [3], this mostly affects small-scale projects. Such occupancy stability is evident in Switzerland’s urban centers, particularly Zurich, where sustained housing demand (long-term vacancy rate <1% [7]) and legally mandated occupancy limits minimize variability. Thus, user counts constitute a methodologically robust basis for analysis. For comparison, the conventional per-floor-area metric (officially *per ERA* in Switzerland) is concurrently reported.

Figure 1: CRLCA scope by scenario: life-cycle modules are defined according to the EN 15978 standard. White modules are excluded; only black modules occurring after the decision-making point (in gray) are included.

2.2. System boundaries with CRLCA

Figure 1 outlines the CRLCA system boundaries for the three scenarios, covering post-decision new construction, refurbishment, and demolition. Embodied carbon includes A1–A5 for new construction, B5 for refurbishment, and C1 for end-of-life demolition. Operational carbon is included post-decision B6 (operational energy) and B7 (operational water) for both newly constructed and refurbished buildings. The time boundary remains open, but analysis focuses on performance through 2050, aligned with Switzerland’s net-zero target. Component replacement cycles (B4) are excluded due to their temporal distance from the decision point and the high uncertainty of events occurring 25 years later, which weakens causal attribution. Embodied carbon thus captures the entire initial carbon load before use, known as the “carbon spike”.

2.3. Temporal abstraction for stock-level CRLCA

A key challenge in stock-level CRLCA is variation in project implementation years, hindering consistent modeling and comparability. As policy analysis prioritizes collective outcomes over individual project trajectories, this study therefore adopts a **consolidated decision time** to approximate stock-level performance across varied implementation timelines. This abstraction

affects only operational carbon, which accumulates over time, while embodied carbon is fixed, as it is emitted in the initial phase. Moreover, unlike operational carbon, studies show that embodied carbon intensity does not consistently decline over time, supporting a time-independent treatment. Although simultaneous implementation of all projects is unrealistic due to resource constraints, this simplification provides a reasonable proxy for stock-level modeling.

Operational emissions are assessed through three cases: (1) boundary scenarios (earliest and latest implementation years), and (2) a GFA-weighted average year that reflects the central tendency of implementation timing while accounting for the scale-dependent nature of operational carbon relative to floor area. Although this average best approximates gradual implementation, it introduces a temporal compression bias that modestly underestimates cumulative operational emissions and delays carbon payback, slightly overestimating CPBT. This $\sim 10\%$ downward bias, estimated using an idealized matrix-based timing model, is confined to the projects' implementation period and diminishes over time. Beyond the 2013 GFA-weighted average (marking the first *inward development* policy cycle), three tentative consolidated timings are tested to explore policy timing effects: 2010 (earlier than actual implementation), 2016 and 2019 (later, with 2019 tied to the upcoming planning revision). Implementation across 335 RBR projects falls between the 2010 and 2013 cases, aligning most closely with the latter.

2.4. Range-bound analysis

This study examines 335 building projects—both demolished and newly constructed—across varied periods, materials, and techniques. Given substantial heterogeneity and the lack of material-specific data in existing databases, detailed project-level assessments for precise evaluation prove infeasible. These limitations raise a methodological question: Do meaningful insights rely on exact estimates? In this context, not necessarily. Rather than investing extensive effort in exact values, the analysis estimates CPBT ranges across scenarios to inform policy. It adopts a **range-bound analysis** based on extreme assumptions (best-case and worst-case) to address data limitations, a method widely used to bound assessment results under uncertainty.

Embodied carbon emissions (G_e) over A1–A5 are estimated by scaling structural carbon (G_s) using ξ (structural share) and ζ (A1–A3 share in A1–A5), following $G_e = G_s / (\xi \times \zeta)$. The G_s values for buildings are first estimated via Softmax-weighted interpolation from 48 Swiss building archetypes with complete superstructure data [8]. Owing to inconsistencies in LCA studies, ξ and ζ vary from 45–60% and 88–96%, respectively. As G_e is a rational function of ξ and ζ , both bounded within $[0, 1]$, it decreases monotonically with respect to their product. This monotonicity supports a range-bound analysis: Estimate I (optimistic setting) assigns upper bounds to both ξ and ζ , minimizing embodied carbon and the initial carbon spike gap; whereas Estimate II (conservative setting) assigns their lower bounds, maximizing both. Assuming equal operational emissions, Estimate I yields the shortest CPBT, whereas Estimate II results in the longest. By the same logic, for B5 refurbishment and C1 demolition, Estimate I adopts 40% and 3.6% of the A1–A5 embodied carbon from equivalent new residential construction, based on their respective literature ranges (36.5–40% and 3.6–5%), thereby narrowing BR's carbon spike gap relative to RN and RO. **Operational carbon emissions** (G_o) are estimated by multiplying the annual reference intensity θ ($\text{kgCO}_2\text{eq}/\text{m}^2$) by GFA. Annual θ values are grouped by construction year (pre-1979, 2000–2009, post-2010), with a separate category for refurbished pre-1979 buildings. θ values after 2019 are derived from the «CO2-Rechner PACTA» tool [9] and benchmarked against actual values in [10], aligned with heating demand defined by SIA 380/1 and Switzerland's 2050 decarbonization pathway. For earlier years without direct references, values are linearly scaled backwards from the 2019 reference using Switzerland's per-area operational decarbonization trajectory (-64.6% , 1990–2022). Only space heating and hot water are included, as they dominate operational emissions given Switzerland's largely CO₂-neutral electricity supply. Post-refurbishment carbon reductions range from 54% (multi-building average in [10]) to 76% (single case in [9]). Estimate I adopts 54%, fitting the range-bound logic

and favoring earlier CPBT for BR by limiting refurbishment's operational advantage.

3. Results & Discussion

Results show that for embodied carbon, both optimistic (I) and conservative (II) estimates place BR as having the highest initial spike across metrics, followed by RN and RO, with the gap widening from estimates I to II. The estimated embodied carbon per ERA (A1–A5, kgCO₂eq/m²) for new construction ranges from 367 (I), aligning with the lower-middle quartiles of the ECB database [11], to 533 (II), approaching its third quartile and exceeding values from comparable studies in Finland [12]. In contrast, for operational carbon, BR consistently has the lowest annual emissions, while RO has the highest. Results for estimate I are shown in Figure 2.

1.- The choice of evaluation metric influences assessment outcomes. Under identical simulation settings, CPBT consistently occurs later with the per capita metric due to differing evaluative perspectives: the per ERA approach normalizes emissions by unit area, emphasizing per-area carbon efficiency; while the per capita metric redistributes area-based emissions across occupants, highlighting the carbon intensity of individual spatial use. The per capita metrics better captures resource consumption intensity and individual environmental responsibility.

2.- When CPBT occurs, emission rank shifts consistently follow: RN surpasses RO, then BR surpasses RO, and finally BR surpasses RN, though not all are observed in each simulation.

3.- The timing of decisions shapes CPBT outcomes. Later decisions reduce the likelihood of achieving CPBT and lengthen the required time under both metrics. Although decision years progress linearly from 2010 to 2019, delays become increasingly pronounced. This nonlinearity reflects Switzerland's decarbonization trend, which narrows energy efficiency differences across the building stock and weakens the operational carbon advantage of new construction. The **2013** simulation approximates the actual emission profile of the 335 RBR projects, where BR reaches CPBT over RN and RO in 2036/2037 per capita, and 2030/2031 per ERA. In the **2019** simulation, under the per capita metric, emissions converge by 2050 but retain their initial

Simulation under optimistic conditions (Estimate I): (a) embodied emissions: $\xi = 60\%$, $\zeta = 96\%$; (b) warm demand: 100% of operational emissions; (c) 54% operational emissions reduction via refurbishment; (d) decision-time in 2013, 2016, 2019, respectively; (e) net-zero by 2050.

Figure 2: Cumulative carbon emissions under optimistic estimate I, measured per ERA (left) and per capita (right), under the assumption of consolidated decision years in 2013, 2016, and 2019.

ranking—BR remains highest, with no CPBT; under ERA, RN overtakes RO in 2047, while BR stays highest, with marginal gaps by 2050. Per capita results identify **2016** as a turning point, beyond which BR consistently ranks as the least favorable scenario. Had decisions been made in **2010**, CPBT for BR would occur after nearly 19 years per capita and 15 years per ERA.

The actual CPBT for the 335 RBR projects falls between the 2010 and 2013 results, averages 16 years per ERA, and aligns most closely with the 2013 BR simulation. This exceeds the 10-year estimate in Germany’s 2012 report [13], which did not account for decarbonization. After 2019, BR becomes the highest-emission option without reaching CPBT, consistent with findings for a public school in Finland [12]. Notably, these results persist even under optimistic assumptions (Estimate I), where BR more readily approaches CPBT; however, the full simulation range (from I to II) reveals increasing difficulty for BR to reach carbon payback, further reinforcing its unfavorable outlook. These findings also extend to public buildings, which have lower operational- but higher embodied carbon intensity, further limiting the potential for operational savings to compensate for upfront emissions, making BR even less sustainable.

4. Conclusions

This study applied a stock-level CRLCA with range-bound analysis to evaluate the carbon payback of 335 residential projects in Zurich under three construction scenarios. Results show that post-2019 replacements, under both metrics, no longer achieve sufficient operational emission savings to justify their embodied carbon investments. The finding supports prioritizing refurbishment over replacement in current and future climate strategies and calls for a reappraisal of the *inward development* policy and low-emission densification pathways. The justification of construction strategies and related policies is time-sensitive and should be reassessed as conditions evolve. Moreover, the consistent tendency of per capita metrics to yield more conservative outcomes than per area metrics underscores their strength in capturing individual-level accountability and informing participatory, citizen-responsive policy. This distinction reinforces the critical role of metric selection in shaping fit-for-purpose evaluation frameworks.

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